

Investigation of Primary School Teachers' Attitudes and Motivations About Distance Learning During the Pandemic Period

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Abstract – The purpose of this study is to identify teachers' attitudes and professional motivations regarding distance learning during the pandemic process. The descriptive research method, a quantitative research method, was used in the study. “Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process” and “Teacher Motivation Scale” were used in the study. The study consists of 350 primary school teachers working in Konya during the 2020-2021 school year. According to the results of the study, it was concluded that the professional motivation of the teachers regarding distance learning during the pandemic process was at a high level, and their attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments were at a moderate level. It was observed according to the results of Pearson correlation analysis that there was a significant and positive relationship between teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments and their professional motivation.

Keywords: Pandemic Process, Professional Motivation, Attitude, Distance Learning.

Introduction

The coronavirus pandemic that occurred in China in December 2019 influenced the whole world in a short period of time. The pandemic process has also resulted in accompanying problems and changes in learning. The closure of schools and the transition to distance learning to maintain learning bring forth various difficulties for teachers, students, and parents (Chang & Yano, 2020). The internet problems faced by teachers in their area, their proficiency in computer use, their status to access students, and the anxiety caused by the pandemic process result in a situation required to be investigated (Mulenga & Marbán, 2020).

Although the definitions of distance and online learning are very different, according to Holmberg (1986), they include ways of studying at all levels out of the control of teachers. In this way, students can assume their own responsibilities in learning. Distance learning is defined as the learning system where communication is provided by people who are in areas independent of each other in terms of time and space through technological tools and equipment (computers, tablets, phones, etc.) (Aydemir, 2018). In other words, it is formal learning that connects learning groups, instructors, and resources from different fields through communication technologies (Simonson & Schlosser, 2009). Teachers come to the forefront with their guiding features that guide and instruct students on how to learn rather than conveying information directly (Yıldırım, 2020).

Considering the conditions introduced by the information age, the most important factor for the development of a society and moving with the times is learning. Therefore, distance learning plays a crucial role. Relevant institutions and organizations are expected to give due consideration to distance learning. Today, the interest and importance in distance learning gradually increase with the developing information and communication technology (Adıyaman, 2002).

Traditional face-to-face learning is believed to be very effective in learning so far (Sutiah, Slamet, Shafat & Supriyono, 2020). However, with the pandemic, it was decided the transition to distance

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learning to maintain learning (YÖK, 2020). Distance learning is education that does not require teachers and students to be together spatially and temporally (Fırat, 2016). Today, distance learning is commonly used at all levels of learning. A good infrastructure depends on many factors such as institutional support in order to carry out distance learning effectively and efficiently (Markova, Glazkova & Zaborova, 2017).

Motivation is to act with the necessary intrinsic or extrinsic motivation to perform an activity for a purpose and to wait for the desired outcome (Ryan & Deci, 2000). According to Wlodkowski (1985), motivation is expressed as a process that directs behavior and ensures the sustainability of behavior, and provides specific behavioral choices in the direction of objectives. Motivation is the exertion of a specific effort by individuals in the direction of their interests and desires for the objectives they want to achieve. While it is considered that individuals can be more motivated about the tasks they will confront later on as a result of those they performed successfully, it is thought that it is more difficult to motivate and achieve the tasks for unsuccessful people.

Attitude is the reflection ways of the situation, feelings, and behaviors of an individual (Baykara Pehlivan, 2008). According to İnceoğlu (2004), attitude is defined as a possible behavior that an individual's behavior is expected to exhibit against any event, is closely related to the environment in which he lives and the environment he is in, etc. An individual can't develop an attitude regarding every situation. However, he is expected to exhibit attitudes regarding psychologically important situations influencing him. Attitudes enable individuals to exhibit harmonious behaviors. Attitudes are formed and supported by learning. Attitudes show a variable structure due to constantly changing living conditions.

This study investigates the relationship between the attitudes regarding distance learning and the professional motivations of primary school teachers working in Konya during the pandemic process. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between the attitudes of distance learning teachers and their professional motivations during the pandemic process. In line with these purposes, answers to sub-problems were sought.

1. What is the professional motivation of teachers regarding distance learning during the pandemic process?
2. What are the teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process?
3. Is there any relationship between teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments and professional motivations during the pandemic process, according to the gender variable?
4. Is there any relationship between teachers' attitudes regarding distance learning during the pandemic process in terms of the following?
 - 4.1. Professional seniority year
 - 4.2. Age
5. Is there any relationship between teachers' professional motivations during the pandemic process in terms of the following?
 - 5.1. Professional seniority year
 - 5.2. Age
6. Is there any relationship between the attitude scale regarding the use of distance learning environments and the teachers' professional motivation scale?

Method

Research Design

This study aims to reveal the opinions of information and IT teachers about distance learning during the pandemic period. The descriptive research method, which is a quantitative research method, was used in the study. The descriptive research method records the relationships between the cases by

identifying and listing these relationships and tries to reveal the relationships and features between the current situations as is (Yıldırım, 2000).

Study Group

The study group of the research consists of primary school teachers selected by simple random sampling method in different public schools located in Konya. The reason for selecting the random method is that each unit preferred in the study group has an equal probability of being selected in the target population.

In order to use the simple random sampling method in this study, primary schools in Konya center (Selçuklu, Meram, Karatay) are listed first. The study group was determined randomly from the listed schools. The units selected in the study do not influence the unselected units. The study group of the research consists of 350 teachers working in Konya primary schools.

Table 1. Demographic data of the participants

	Variable	f	%
Gender	Female	260	74.3
	Male	90	25.7
	Total	350	100
Professional Seniority	1-10 years	100	28.6
	11-20 years	99	28.3
	21-30 years	127	36.3
	31-40 years	24	6.9
	Total	350	100
Age	Between 20-30	78	22.3
	Between 31-40	69	19.7
	41 and over	203	58.0
	Total	350	100

The demographic data of the participants are shown in Table 3.1. When Table 3.1 and the years of professional seniority of the teachers who participated in the study are analyzed, it is seen that 100 of them have been working between 1 and 10 years, 99 between 11 and 20 years, 127 between 21 and 30 years, and 24 between 31 and 40 years. It is observed that 203 of the teachers are aged 41 and over, 78 of them are between the ages of 20 and 30, and 69 of them are between the ages of 31 and 40. The study consists of 260 female and 90 male teachers.

Research Instruments and Processes

Demographic Information Form

A demographic Information Form consisting of a total of three questions was prepared for the teachers and applied to the participants to obtain information about demographic characteristics such as years of gender, Professional seniority and age status for the teachers who participated in the study.

Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process.

“Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process” developed by Yıldız, Çengel & Alkan (2021) was used. This scale was applied to determine the attitudes of teachers in different branches regarding distance learning. The 5-point Likert-type scale consists of four dimensions and 24 items. The rating method was used for each question as strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree. The sub-dimensions are as follows; competence and motivation (7 items), usefulness (8 items), effectiveness (5 items), and satisfaction (4 items). The total variance of the 24-item scale was calculated as 73.42%. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale calculated with Cronbach Alpha was determined as .93.

Teacher Motivation Scale

The “Teacher Motivation Scale” developed by Polat (2010) was used. This scale was applied to identify the opinions of teachers in different branches about their professional motivation. The rating

method was used for each question as strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree. The 5-point Likert-type scale consists of 24 items and two sub-dimensions. Sub-dimensions and item dimensions are as follows: extrinsic motivation (12 items) and intrinsic motivation (12 items). According to the results of the factor analysis, the total variance of the 24-item scale was calculated as 49.9%. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale calculated with Cronbach Alpha was determined as .91.

Data Collection Process

After the necessary permissions were obtained for the scales to be used in the research, the scales were duplicated and distributed to schools and also linked to school teacher groups through principals or assistant principals. In this way, many participants were reached through Google Forms due to the pandemic. Necessary information about demographic information form and scales was given by the researcher. Data were collected without asking for personal information such as name and surname. In the first part of the data collection, a demographic information form regarding the personal information of the teachers was used. In the second part, the attitude scale regarding the use of distance education environments in the pandemic process consisting of 24 items and the teacher Professional motivation scale consisting of 24 items were applied.

Data Analysis

The scales were reproduced, and both were distributed to schools and sent to school teacher groups as a link via principals or assistant principals, after obtaining the necessary permits for the scales to be used in the study. Thus, many participants were accessed through Google Forms because of the pandemic. The researchers provided background information on demographic information forms and scales. Data were collected without requiring personal particulars such as name and surname. In the collection of data, the demographic information form regarding teachers' personal particulars was used in the first part. In the second part, it was applied the attitude scale regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process consisting of 24 items, and the teachers' professional motivation scale consisting of 24 items.

The data collected with the data collection tools in the research were transferred to the computer environment and analyzed with the SPSS program. First, descriptive statistical analyzes (number of people, average, and percentage) were applied, and tabulations were made in the direction of the results. It was investigated the arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of the scores obtained from both scales used in the study. T-Test was used to determine whether or not the teachers who participated in the study differed according to the variables discussed in two dimensions, and ANOVA, a one-way analysis of variance, was used for the variables considered in more than two dimensions. Pearson correlation analysis was used to identify the aspect, level, and amount of the relationship between the attitude regarding the use of distance learning environments and the professional motivation scale's mean scores during the pandemic process.

Findings

In the direction of the purposes of the study, the results of the responses given by 350 teachers are explained in the tables below in the sequences and titles given in the objectives.

Teachers' Professional Motivation for Distance Learning during the Pandemic Process

The data were interpreted according to Table 2. while calculating the evaluation criteria in the table, the formula according to the 5-point Likert type (highest value-lowest value)/evaluation range (low, medium and high) ($5-1=4$; $4/3=1.33$) was taken into consideration.

Table 2. Scale Evaluation Range and Criterion Values

Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale	Variable
1.0-2.33	Low Level
2.34-3.66	Moderate Level
3.67-5.00	High Level

The responses of the teachers to the "Professional Motivation Scale" were investigated and presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Professional Motivation of Teachers

Item No	\bar{X}	S	Status
1	4.3429	.84443	High
2	4.1629	1.05401	High
3	4.1114	1.06340	High
4	4.6314	.70091	High
5	4.5171	.87532	High
6	4.6000	.84636	High
7	4.3857	.97082	High
8	4.5114	.75976	High
9	4.3171	.98382	High
10	4.1543	1.14265	High
11	4.1600	.91945	High
12	3.3400	1.44482	Moderate
13	3.6200	1.22118	Moderate
14	4.5543	.74647	High
15	4.1486	1.07894	High
16	4.3714	.96606	High
17	4.4457	1.01911	High
18	3.2514	1.48910	Moderate
19	4.2114	1.15844	High
20	3.3686	1.56562	Moderate
21	3.7800	1.45028	High
22	3.6457	1.42035	Moderate
23	4.0571	1.29453	High
24	2.6943	1.44259	Moderate
General Average	4.0576	1.102434	High

When Table 3., is analyzed, it is seen that the professional motivation of the teachers is high ($\bar{x}=4.05$). In this respect, it can be said that the professional motivation of the teachers regarding distance learning is at a high level.

When the items are examined, we see that the professional motivation of teachers is high in all items i.e. they consider that they are successful in their job (Item No: 1) ($\bar{x}=4.34$), they believe that the work they do is worthwhile (Item No:4) ($\bar{x}=4.63$), and they think that the physical conditions are appropriate in the working environment (Article No:11) ($\bar{x}=4.16$) (Table 3.).

Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process

The data were interpreted according to Table 4. While calculating the evaluation criteria in the table, the formula according to the 5-point Likert type (highest value-lowest value)/evaluation range (low, medium and high) ($5-1=4$; $4/3=1.33$) was taken into consideration.

Table 4. Scale Evaluation Range and Criterion Values

Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process	Variable
1.0-2.33	Low Level
2.34-3.66	Moderate Level
3.67-5.00	High Level

The responses of the teachers to the “Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process” were investigated and presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Attitudes of Teachers Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process

Item No	\bar{X}	S	Status
1	3.0857	1.23630	Moderate
2	2.3600	1.31188	Moderate
3	3.5514	1.32485	Moderate
4	3.0485	1.34588	Moderate
5	2.1171	1.30043	Low
6	2.7342	1.23730	Moderate
7	3.4543	1.28108	Moderate
8	3.4343	1.17274	Moderate
9	2.3714	1.08877	Moderate
10	2.6943	1.30053	Moderate
11	3.8057	.96469	High
12	2.5229	1.29725	Moderate
13	3.2800	1.26055	Moderate
14	3.9514	1.05463	High
15	3.6143	1.19085	Moderate
16	3.5686	1.15038	Moderate
17	2.0371	1.22359	Low
18	3.6486	1.15773	Moderate
19	3.2457	1.16892	Moderate
20	3.0143	1.40907	Moderate
21	2.9629	1.30956	Moderate
22	3.3029	1.24147	Moderate
23	3.2714	1.26130	Moderate
24	3.2343	1.13903	Moderate
General Average	3.0963	1.226199	Moderate

When Table 5., is examined, it is seen that teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process are moderate ($\bar{x}=3.09$). Therefore, it can be said that teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process are moderate.

When the items are examined, we see that the performance evaluations are moderate in all of the items in terms of attitude regarding performance evaluation, i.e., the thought that teachers take pleasure in using the distance learning platform (Item No: 1) ($\bar{x}=3,08$), the thought that they consider the distance learning platform complex (Item No: 9) ($\bar{x}=2.37$), and the thought of being pleased with the feedback they received from the students (Item No:21) ($\bar{x}=2.96$) (Table 5.).

Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process and Professional Motivations according to Gender

Attitudes of teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments and their professional motivations were investigated according to their gender. Accordingly, the T-Test was made to determine whether there was a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers. The results obtained are given in Table 6.

Table 6. T-Test results of the Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments and Professional Motivations According to Gender

	Gender	N	\bar{X}	S	Sd	t	p
Attitude Scale Regarding Distance Learning Professional Motivation Scale	Female	260	3.0970	0.75047	348	-.770	0.44
	Male	90	3.1666	0.70110			
	Female	260	4.1426	0.69002	348	3.975	0.00
	Male	90	3.8120	0.64960			
	Toplam	297					

* $p < .05$.

When Table 6. is examined, it is seen that there is no difference between the teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process according to gender ($t_{(348)} = -.770$, $p > .05$). However, it occurs that the mean scores of male teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments ($\bar{x}=3,166$) are higher than the mean scores of female teachers ($\bar{x}=3,097$). On the other hand, when Table 6. is examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference in terms of professional motivation scores of teachers ($t_{(348)} = 3.975$, $p < .05$). However, it is seen that the professional motivation of female teachers ($\bar{x}=4.142$) is higher than male teachers ($\bar{x}=3.812$).

Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process according to the Year of Professional Seniority and Age Variable

Attitude of teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process were investigated according to the years of professional seniority and age. Accordingly, whether or not there is a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers and the results obtained are given under subtitles.

Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process according to the Year of Professional Seniority

Attitude of teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process were investigated according to their years of professional seniority. The Anova-Test was made to determine whether there was a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers. The results obtained are given in Table 7.

Table 7. Anova Test Results of the Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments According to the Year of Professional Seniority

		Year of Seniority	N	\bar{X}	S
Attitude Scale Regarding Distance Learning the Pandemic Process	1-10 years	100	3.3228	.72804	
	11-20 years	99	3.1414	.71554	
	21-30 years	127	2.9675	.76236	
	31-40 years	24	2.9200	.51075	
Total			350	3.1149	.73773

Table 8. was used for the interpretation of the data in Table 7.

Table 8. The Attitudes of Teachers Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments During the Pandemic Process were Investigated According to Their Years of Professional Seniority

	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Intergroup	8.060	3	2.686	5.111	.002
Intragroup	181.882	346	.525		
Total	189.943	349			

* $p < .05$.

As can be seen in Table 8., it is seen a significant difference [$F(3-346)=5,111$, $p < .05$] when examining the responses given by the teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process according to their professional seniority whether or not differ according to the one-way analysis of variance. The use of distance learning environments by teachers during the pandemic process differs according to the years of professional seniority. A post hoc (TUKEY) test was performed to find out between which groups this difference was. As a result of the test, it was found that there are teachers who have worked between 21 and 30 years of professional seniority, and teachers who have worked in other years of seniority, according to degrees.

Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments during the Pandemic Process according to their Ages

Attitudes of teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process were investigated according to their ages. The Anova-Test was made to determine whether there was a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers. The results obtained are given in Table 9.

Table 9. Anova Test Results of the Investigation of Teachers' Attitudes Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments According to Their Ages

		Age	N	\bar{X}	S
Attitude Scale Regarding Distance Learning the Pandemic Process	Between 21-30	78	3.3307	.70782	
	Between 31-40	69	3.2771	.77746	
	41 and over	203	2.9769	.70693	
Total			350	3.1149	.73773

Table 10. was used for the interpretation of the data in Table 9.

Table 10. The Attitudes of Teachers Regarding the use of Distance Learning Environments During the Pandemic Process were Investigated According to Their Ages

	Sum of Suares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Intergroup	9.313	2	4.656	8.945	.000
Intragroup	180.629	347	.521		
Total	189.943	349			

* $p < .05$.

As can be seen in Table 10., it is seen a significant difference [$F(2-347)=8,945$, $p < .05$], when examining the responses given by the teachers regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process according to their age whether or not differ according to the one-way analysis of variance. The use of distance learning environments by teachers during the pandemic process differs according to their age. A post hoc (TUKEY) test was performed to find out between which groups this difference was. According to the test results, it is seen that there is a difference between teachers aged 41 and over and teachers in other age groups.

Investigation of Teachers' Professional Motivation according to Year of Professional Seniority

The professional motivations of teachers were investigated according to their professional seniority and age. Accordingly, whether or not there is a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers and the results obtained are given under subtitles

Investigation of Teachers' Professional Motivation according to Year of Professional Seniority

The professional motivations of teachers were investigated according to their professional seniority and age. Accordingly, the Anova-Test was made to determine whether there was a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers. Results obtained are given in Table 11.

Table 11. Anova Test Results of the Investigation of Professional Motivation of Teachers According to Their Years of Professional Seniority

	Year of Seniority	N	\bar{X}	S
Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale	1-10 years	100	4.1866	.6653
	11-20 years	99	3.9642	.8288
	21-30 years	127	4.1095	.5625
	31-40 years	24	3.6302	.6564
Total		350	4.0576	.6941

Table 12. was used for he interpretation of the data in Table 11.

Table 12. Teachers' professional motivations were investigated according to the years of professional seniority.

	Sum of Suares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Intergroup	7.256	3	2.418	5.200	.002
Intragroup	160.925	346	.465		
Total	168.181	349			

* $p < .05$.

As can be seen in Table 12., it is seen a significant difference [$F(3-346)=5,200$, $p < .05$], when examining the responses given by the teachers on professional motivation according to their years of professional seniority whether or not differ according to the one-way analysis of variance. The use of distance learning environments by teachers during the pandemic process differs according to their age. A post hoc (TUKEY) test was performed to find out between which groups this difference was. According to the degrees as a result of the test, it was determined that there were teachers whose

professional seniority is between 21 and 30 years and teachers who were between 1 and 10 years, 11 and 20 years, and 31 and 40 years.

Investigation of Teachers' Professional Motivation according to their Ages

Teachers' Professional Motivation were investigated according to their ages. The Anova-Test was made to determine whether there was a significant difference between the responses given by the teachers. Results obtained are given in Table 13.

Table 13. Anova Test Results of the Investigation of The Professional Motivation of Teachers According to Their Ages

				Age	N	\bar{X}	S
Attitude Scale	Regarding	Distance	Between 21-30	78	4.1458	.72647	
Learning During the Pandemic Process	Between 31-40		69	4.1787	.77264		
	41 and over		203	3.9825	.64557		
Total				350	4.0576	.69418	

Table 14. was used for the interpretation of the data in Table 13.

Table 14. Teachers' professional motivations were investigated according to their ages

	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Intergroup	2.763	2	1.381	2.898	.056
Intragroup	165.418	347	.477		
Total	168.181	349			

* $p < .05$.

As can be seen in Table 14., it is seen that there is no significant difference [$F(2-347)=2,898, p > .05$], when examining the responses given by the teachers on professional motivation according to their ages whether or not differ according to the one-way analysis of variance. Professional motivations of teachers do not differ according to their age.

Investigation of the Relationship between the Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments and the Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale

The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated to determine whether or not there is a significant difference between teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process and their professional motivation. The results obtained are given in Table 15.

Table 15. Investigation of The Relationship Between The Attitude Scale Regarding The Use of Distance Learning Environments and The Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale

		Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments	Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale
Attitude Scale Regarding the Use of Distance Learning Environments	Pearson Correlation	1	.430**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	350	350
Teachers' Professional Motivation Scale	Pearson Correlation	.430**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	350	350

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

When examining Table 15., it is seen that there is a significant and positive relationship between teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments and teachers' Professional motivations ($r=.430, p < .000$).

Conclusion, Discussion and Suggestions

The study consists of 350 teachers working in primary schools in Konya. Teachers were applied the demographic information form, the attitude scale regarding distance learning during the pandemic process, the professional motivation scale, and the forms intending to reveal their opinions on distance learning, and the data were analyzed. 74.3% of the teachers who participated in the study are female, and 25.7% are male. While 36.3% of the participants have professional seniority between 21 and 30 years, 28.6% between 1 and 10 years, 28.3% between 11- and 20 years, and 6.9% between 31 and 40 years during their duty. While 58% of the teachers who participated in the study are 41 and over, 22.3% are between the ages of 20 and 30, and 19.7% are between the ages of 31 and 40.

As a result of the examination of the professional motivations of the teachers during the pandemic process according to the scale evaluation and criterion values, it is seen that their professional motivation is high ($\bar{x}=4.05$). According to the qualitative study performed by Bakırcı, Dođdu and Artun (2021) with science teachers during the pandemic period, teachers mentioned that the distance learning period contributed to their professional development, and thus they had knowledge of many computer programs, software, and hardware. It is also expressed that the professional motivation of teachers increases together with their professional development.

As a result of the investigation of teachers in regard to their attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process, it is considered that their attitudes are moderate ($\bar{x}=3.09$). In the study performed by Karakuş and Erşen (2021), with the participation of 150 teachers, they concluded that teachers' attitudes regarding distance learning were negative during the Covid-19 pandemic. According to the study by Moçoşođlu and Kaya (2020), they concluded that teachers' attitudes regarding distance learning were also negative. According to the study of Ülkü (2018), primary school teachers their attitudes towards it seem to be positive. Negative attitude towards distance education the common aspect of the studies developed is that these studies were carried out during the Covid-19 pandemic process.

It is seen that there is no difference if the teacher's attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process are examined according to the gender variable. In the study performed by Karakuş and Erşen (2021), a significant difference can be mentioned when the attitudes of teachers regarding distance learning are examined according to the gender variable. It is seen that the attitude scores of male teachers are higher than female teachers. When examining in regards to professional motivation, it is seen that there is a significant difference according to the gender variables of the teachers. It is seen in the study performed by Altunok and İşcan (2021) that there is no significant difference in the professional motivation of teachers according to age, gender, seniority, and marital status. In the study conducted by Argon and Ertürk (2013), teachers it is seen that occupational motivations do not change according to the gender variable.

It is seen that there is a significant difference if teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process are examined according to their professional seniority. In the study performed by Kocayıđıt and Uşun (2020), with the participation of 204 teachers, it is seen that teachers' attitudes regarding distance learning differ according to their professional seniority. It is observed that there is a significant difference if the professional motivation of the teachers who participated in the study is examined according to the year of seniority.

It is seen that there is a significant difference if the ages of teachers are examined regarding the use of distance learning environments during the pandemic process. When examining the professional motivation of teachers according to their ages, it is seen that there is no significant difference between the ages of the teachers.

In the direction of the conclusion of the study, it is seen that teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments are moderate. Therefore, teachers working in primary schools can be given in-service seminars and training on distance learning through distance learning programs. They can be informed about the importance of using distance learning environments and their contribution

to their professional development. According to the conclusions of the study, it is seen that teachers' attitudes regarding the use of their environments show a significant difference only concerning the variables of seniority and age. In the direction of result, teachers who have worked between 31 and 40 years, classroom teachers, and teachers who are over 41 years old can be informed about the use of distance learning environments, and they can be provided to improve themselves in this regard.

This study only consists of teachers who are working. Future studies can be performed with prospective teachers. In order for teacher candidates to improve their knowledge and skills about distance learning, training programs can be organized that will be better equipped for distance learning and contribute to their professional development. In this study, teachers' attitudes regarding the use of distance learning environments and their professional motivations during the Covid-19 pandemic were identified. Since the Covid-19 pandemic process is a temporary process, a new study can be performed with teachers about the use of distance learning environments after the pandemic.

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